

ACCELERATED TESTING FOR LONG-TERM DURABILITY OF FRP LAMINATES FOR MARINE USE

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ABSTRACT: Our proposed accelerated testing methodology for the long term durability of polymer composites is based on the time-temperature superposition principle to be held for the viscoelasticity of polymer matrix. The long term flexural fatigue life of plain woven carbon fiber/vinylester (CFRP) laminates for advanced marine use was predicted based on the proposed methodology, comparing with that of glass fiber /vinylester (GFRP) for conventional marine use. The flexural fatigue strengths of CFRP laminates as well as that of GFRP laminates decreases strongly with increasing time and temperature. The dependence of flexural strength upon the number of load-cycles to failure demonstrates remarkable difference for CFRP laminates and GFRP laminates; the strength of latter decreases strongly with increasing number of cycles to failure while that of the former does only slightly.

KEYWORDS: Life prediction, Fatigue, Time-temperature dependence, Viscoelasticity

INTRODUCTION

Developing a testing procedure to establish the lifetimes of materials in extreme service environments is becoming a high priority. With service lifetimes measured in years, it is almost unthinkable to do real time testing under a variety of conditions. Existing accelerated testing methodologies for metals cannot be simply applied to composite materials, since these methodologies are not intended for viscoelastic materials such as polymeric composite materials, which exhibit strong time and temperature dependencies.

Our accelerated testing methodology is based on the time-temperature superposition principle for polymeric materials. This principle was originally developed for non-destructive material properties, but recent studies have shown that it can also be applied to failure properties of composite materials. Using this principle as the building block, we have developed a methodology to predict the long-term life of composite materials, such as the static (constant strain rate: CSR) strength, creep life, and fatigue life.

In this paper, the long term flexural fatigue life of plain woven carbon fiber/vinylester (CFRP) laminates for advanced marine use is predicted based on the methodology, comparing with that of glass fiber /vinylester (GFRP) for conventional marine use.

PREDICTION PROCEDURE OF FATIGUE LIFE

Accelerated testing methodologies for metals have been studied for some time, but not enough studies have been performed on polymer composites. One of the most popular tools used to predict the fatigue life of metals is the S-N curve, which is based on the assumption that fatigue life depends on cycles, but not on time. Accelerating the test is an easy task using the S-N curves, since the cyclic loads can be applied at much higher frequencies than the actual loading.

Unlike metals, polymer composites are viscoelastic and their properties exhibit strong time and temperature dependency. For this reason, simply applying the S-N curve to polymer composites will not provide accurate prediction of the fatigue life. Accelerating the test becomes a difficult task, since

time plays an important role in the fatigue and creep of polymer composites. Therefore, we need to develop a new accelerated testing methodology more suited for polymer composites.

Our accelerated testing methodology is based on the time-temperature superposition principle of polymeric materials. This principle has been widely employed to characterize the nondestructive properties, and recently, has shown remarkable success in characterizing the failure properties of polymer composites. In this case, elevated temperature states are used to accelerate the mechanical degradations, which occur under loads over long period of time at lower temperature. Using this as our building block, we have developed a methodology to predict the long-term life of polymer composites under various temperatures and loading conditions, such as constant strain rate (CSR), creep, and fatigue loadings.

Figure 1 shows the outline of our accelerated testing methodology. The four hypotheses shown at the middle of this figure are the conditions that must be met in order for the methodology to work properly. These hypotheses will be tested in order to validate and possibly provide limit to the applicability of the methodology.

Hypothesis A states and assumes that the failure mechanisms under CSR, creep, and fatigue loading are identical. This allows us to relate these three different loading types as follows. Here, a creep loading is considered as a fatigue loading with stress ratio of $R=\sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max}=1$, and a CSR loading is considered to be equivalent to a half cycle of fatigue loading with $R=0$.

The CSR test data for different temperatures are shifted along the logarithmic scale of time to form a smooth curve called the master curve at a suitably chosen reference temperature. The amounts of these shifts are called time-temperature shift factors. In the plot of the master curve, the vertical axis is the strength, and the horizontal axis is the combination of temperature and time to failure, which we call the reduced time to failure. The significance of this master curve is that it can be used to predict the strength under any combinations of temperature and time to failure.

Hypothesis B states that the same time-temperature superposition principle applies for all three types of strengths (CSR, creep, and fatigue). In other words, we can use the same values of shift factors for all three types of strengths.

Hypothesis C states that the linear cumulative damage law can be used for monotonic loading. This allows us to estimate the life under complex loading, by summing up the damages for individual load steps.

The prediction curves of the fatigue life are constructed from the CSR master curve and S-N curves at a single frequency and various temperatures, according to the Hypotheses A and B. The fatigue master curves are plotted with the applied stress amplitude as the vertical axis, and the reduced time to failure as the horizontal axis. Different curves represent different cycles to failure. These fatigue master curves can be used to predict the fatigue life under any combinations of temperature, time to failure, and cycles to failure. Note that the results are applicable only to the case of stress ratio $R=0$.

Our last hypothesis, Hypothesis D, states the linear dependence of fatigue strength upon the stress ratio R . Using this hypothesis, we can plot fatigue master curves for various stress ratio values.

Figure 1 Prediction procedure of fatigue failure strength for FRP

Most commonly used methods of fatigue life prediction are "point-design", which can only predict fatigue life under certain loading condition and temperature. The result can not be used for different loading conditions or temperatures, making it less useful for the real design. Building a useful database for design can be very expensive and time-consuming, if not impossible.

When all four hypotheses hold, our methodology can predict life under any loading conditions, temperature, time to failure, and cycles to failure. By this method, building a useful database for design can be done in relatively short period of time. The methodology can also be used for material screening and selections.

The methodology has been tested for various test configurations, ranging from basic properties to complex systems such as bonded and bolted joints. Let us look closely at the recently obtained results of plain woven carbon fiber/vinylester (CFRP) laminates for advanced marine use, comparing with that of plain woven glass fiber/vinylester (GFRP) laminates for conventional marine use obtained previously.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The constitutions and curing conditions of CFRP laminates T300/VE and GFRP laminates E glass/VE, are shown in table 1.

Table 1 The constitution and curing conditions

	T300/VE	E glass/VE
Fiber	Plain woven cloth of T300 carbon fiber (Toray Industries, Inc.)	Plain woven cloth of E glass fiber (Nitto Boseki Co., Ltd.)
Matrix resin	DERAKANE MOMENTUM 411-350 (The Dow Chemical Company)	RIPOXY R-806 (Showa Highpolymer Co., Ltd.)
Number of layers	9	16
Thickness	2mm	3 mm
Volume fraction of fiber	52%	54%
Curing conditions	R.T.x48h+150°C x2h	R.T.x48h+80°Cx3h+150°C x4h+100°C x24h

The bending tests for T300/VE and E glass/VE laminates were performed for CSR tests, creep tests, and fatigue tests. The testing methods and conditions are shown in Figure 2 and Table 2.

Figure 2 Testing methods

Table 2 Testing conditions

	T300/VE				E glass/VE			
	Deflection rate V [mm]	Frequency f [Hz]	Stress ratio R [$\sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max}$]	Temperature T [°C]	Deflection rate V [mm]	Frequency f [Hz]	Stress ratio R [$\sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max}$]	Temperature T [°C]
CSR	0.02 2 200	-	-	25, 50, 80, 100, 120	0.02 2 200	-	-	50, 80, 90, 100, 110, 115, 120
Fatigue I	-	2	0.05	25, 50, 80, 100	-	2	0.05	50, 80, 100, 110
Creep	-	-	1	25, 80, 100	-	-	1	50, 100, 110
Fatigue II	-	0.02 2	0.05 0.5	25, 100	-	0.02 2	0.05 0.5	50

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We can observe that the failure mechanisms are identical for the three loading conditions for both laminates as shown in Figure 3. This shows that Hypothesis A holds for the flexural properties of these laminates.

Master curve of flexural CSR strength

Figure 4 is the master curves of CSR strength for both laminates. The superposition of the individual segments measured at various constant temperatures forming a smooth master curve indicates that the time-temperature superposition is applicable to the CSR strength of both laminates. Figure 5 shows the shift factors used to create this master curve. Note that the shift factors for the strength of GFRP laminates are almost identical to the shift factors for the storage modulus of vinyl ester resin which is the matrix of CFRP and GFRP laminates, both of which are expressed by two Arrhenius equations having different activation energies. This indicates a relationship between the viscoelastic effect on the stiffness and that on the strength.

Figure 3 Fracture appearance for CSR, creep and fatigue tests

Figure 4 Master curves of flexural CSR strength

(a) T300/VE

(b) E-glass/VE

Figure 5 Time-temperature shift factors of flexural CSR strength

Master curve of flexural creep strength

Figure 6 shows the creep test results and the calculated creep master curve using the linear cumulative damage law. The prediction agrees well with the test results, which shows that Hypothesis C is applicable to these cases.

(a) T300/VE

(b) E-glass/VE

Figure 6 Prediction of flexural creep strength

Master curve of flexural fatigue strength

Figure 7 shows the relations between flexural fatigue strength and number of cycles to failure (S-N curves) with frequencies of $f=2\text{Hz}$ and stress ratio of $R=0$. Note that the applicability of this results is limited to this particular loading condition, and temperatures.

By combining the previous CSR master curves and the S-N curves for both laminates, we can create the fatigue master curves shown in Figure 8. Although limited to the stress ratio of $R=0$, this curves can be used to predict fatigue life under any temperature, time to failure, and cycles to failure.

The lower graphs of Figure 8 show that the flexural fatigue strengths of CFRP laminates as well as that of GFRP laminates decreases strongly with increasing time and temperature. Furthermore, the flexural fatigue strength of CFRP laminates decreases scarcely with increasing the number of load cycles to failure although that of GFRP laminates decreases strongly with increasing the number of load cycles to failure.

(a) T300/VE

(b) E-glass/VE

Figure 7 Flexural fatigue strength versus number of cycles to failure at frequency $f=2\text{Hz}$

(a) T300/VE

(b) E-glass/VE

Figure 8 Master curves of flexural fatigue strength

Figure 9 shows the a S-N curve for a different loading frequencies of $f=0.02\text{Hz}$. When the cycles to failure are the same, the time to failure at this frequencies will be 100 times that for $f=5\text{Hz}$. The prediction agrees well with the actual test results, which shows that Hypothesis B is applicable to this case.

(a) T300/VE

(b) E-glass/VE

Figure 9 Prediction of flexural fatigue strength at frequency $f=0.02\text{Hz}$

Prediction of fatigue failure load for arbitrary load ratio

Figure 10 shows the prediction and the actual test results for the stress ratio of $R=0.5$ for both laminates. The prediction curves were plotted by interpolating the fatigue master curves for $R=0$, and creep master curves which are considered as $R=1$. The prediction and the test results agree, showing that Hypothesis D is applicable to these cases.

(a) T300/VE
(b) E-glass/VE
Figure 10 Prediction of flexural fatigue strength at stress ratio $R=0.5$

CONCLUSION

The proposed methodology has effectively combined the effects of time and temperature on the strength and life of polymer composites. It can be confirmed that the methodology is applicable to the plain woven cloth CFRP laminates for advanced marine use as well as the plain woven cloth GFRP laminates for conventional marine use. It was characterized from the experimental results that the flexural fatigue strengths of CFRP laminates as well as that of GFRP laminates decreases strongly with increasing time and temperature and that the flexural fatigue strength of CFRP laminates decreases scarcely with increasing the number of load cycles to failure although that of GFRP laminates decreases strongly with increasing the number of load cycles to failure.

Our next goal is to find similar relationship using moisture or other agents. A methodology with time-temperature-moisture superposition will enable us to predict life under any temperature and moisture condition, and also allows us to use moisture and other agents to accelerate the tests. Various CFRP laminates of innovative marine composites developed recently is used for this objective.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank the Office of Naval Research for supporting this work through an ONR award with Dr. Yapa Rajapakse as the ONR Program Officer. Our award is numbered to N000140110949 and titled "Long-Term Durability and Damage Tolerance of Innovative Marine Composites (NICOP)". The authors thank Professor Richard Christensen, Stanford University as the consultant of this project, Professor Isao Kimpara and Dr. Koji Yamaguchi, Kanazawa Institute of Technology as the cooperative investigators of this project and Professor Rokuro Muki, UCLA as the theoretical advisor of our research interests. The authors also thank Toray Industries, Inc. as the contributor of CFRP laminates.

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